

Matrix-Based Approach to Optimizing Disassembly Sequence Planning for Aluminum-Framed Windows

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Abstract: The construction industry is under pressure to minimize its environmental impact, especially in environment where resources are limited and ecological concerns are increasing. Disassembly has emerged as a crucial strategy for facilitating material recovery at the end-of-life (EoL) stage. However, the disassembly process remains complex and necessitates strategic planning to optimize material recovery and reduce waste. Unlike most products, windows are larger, more intricate, and composed of multiple materials, layers, and subsystems. This complexity requires comprehensive disassembly planning. Graph-based planning often struggles to accurately capture the extensive range of precedence relations present in complex, multi-material products. To address this limitation, matrix-based representations have been introduced to convert graphical data into computable formats. Matrices can effectively represent geometric, material, and technical precedence relations embedded in 2D cross-section drawings, allowing for the transformation of this information into matrix data that algorithms can use to generate disassembly sequences. This study reviews both adjacency and incidence matrices, employing unweighted and weighted data to develop disassembly sequences. It emphasizes the capabilities of these models in capturing the geometric and material-based relations among aluminum-framed window parts within the parametric modeling environment. Additionally, it identifies key factors, dependencies, and challenges associated with the matrix-based disassembly of multi-material window systems.

Keywords: Disassembly Sequence Planning, Matrix, Parametric Design, Material Recovery, Window

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1 Introduction

The global shift towards resource and material recovery is becoming increasingly important in the built environment, as it helps reduce the environmental impact of the construction industry. By enabling better material recovery through disassembly planning, material re-circulation opportunities alone contribute 60 percent to the CO₂ emissions of industrial production within the EU [1]. EoL can ultimately be defined as the inability for the system to fulfill its design function or meet new requirements [2]. Disassembly sequence planning, which aims to determine the optimal disassembly

sequence, is necessary to enhance efficiency and minimize costs [3]. Considering disassembly constraints is important not only at the end of a product's life but also throughout its life cycle, in order to reduce problems related to its exploitation and maintenance [4]. By identifying the steps to improve disassembly and recovery, this study contributes directly to achieving sustainability goals, such as reducing landfill waste, resource efficiency at the EoL, and reducing carbon footprints.

Integration of Circular Economy (CE) strategies demonstrates how material flow analysis can map material value chains and support sustainable building processes, becoming prominent through the integration of disassembly planning. Aluminum-framed windows, due to their widespread use and high material value, play a pivotal role in circularity through material recovery strategies, such as reuse and recycling. The average lifespan of aluminum windows is approximately 20-25 years, but this can vary depending on the type of window, the level of maintenance, and the local climate. Thanks to its long lifespan, high level of recyclability, and low maintenance requirements, aluminum is an extremely suitable material for durable products in the construction industry. Aluminum-framed windows with their high material recyclability offer a significant opportunity to increase material recovery and conserve resources. This aligns with the broader goal of mitigating resource scarcity and environmental degradation. Additionally, improved recovery practices can reduce costs for manufacturers by reintroducing materials into the production cycle, creating closed-loop systems.

2 Point of Departure

Disassembly plays a key role in the CE, particularly for high-value building products such as windows, during demolition, deconstruction, and the dismantling process. The disassembly process is a progressive dismantling of the core into its assemblies and sub-assemblies through a sequence of tasks [5]. The geometry of the parts needs to be considered when disassembling, as CAD files can provide valuable disassembly knowledge by accessing geometric design information [6]. CAD files as 2D cross-section drawings essentially describe the geometry of each window part profile, their relative position and fit (adjacency), and assembly logic, which indicates who touches whom. Geometric feasibility means it is possible to disassemble two sub-assemblies or parts without collision [6]. Generating geometrically feasible disassembly sequences from non-destructive operations requires collision-free precedence relationships. Therefore, the key aspects of geometric disassembly sequence reasoning are to determine the precedence disassembly relationships correctly and in their entirety [6].

The disassembly process is a complex task that necessitates not only topological precedence relationships but also semantic and technical relationships, as well as material-sensitive relations. These relationships are crucial in generating a feasible and robust disassembly sequence planning. The search for precedence relations is indispensable for proper modeling, because those relations have to be known before establishing the set of basic constraints that must be met by the feasible sub-assemblies [7]. The key aspect of these relationships is their ability to be captured in matrix and graph data forms, which then serve as input for mathematical tools and methods. Matrix-based methods, such as those used in computer handling of disassembly constraint relationships, provide a more convenient means for the computer to handle these complex relationships. To ensure that parts can be disassembled without interfering with each other, collision-free precedence relations can be captured and generated in the Adjacency and Incidence Matrix data format. This evaluation can be carried

out using collision analysis on a 3D assembled window model, where collisions between parts are computed based on topological, spatial relationships, and distances between parts. To streamline the collision test between window parts, the frame profile geometries are converted into bounding boxes, which are used to construct relationships in matrix data format for both adjacency and incidence matrices. Bounding box simplification is used to conduct preliminary collision analysis. When bounding boxes do overlap or touch, the components are considered adjacent or colliding [6]. The adjacency matrix, a square matrix ($n \times n$) that captures direct part-to-part relations as node-to-node connections in this study, in binary data format, is primarily used for topological reasoning. If node i is adjacent to node j , the matrix entry $AM(i,j)$ is 1; otherwise, it is 0. On the other hand, the incidence matrix plays a significant role in algorithms for path finding, optimization, and connectivity analysis. It captures the node-to-edge relations as relationships between parts (nodes) and connections (edges). If a part i is involved in a connection j , the matrix entry $IM(i,j)$ is 1; otherwise, it is 0. Therefore, in this study, we adapted Dijkstra's shortest path algorithm to determine the disassembly sequence of windows by traveling node-to-node or node-to-edge paths in a parametric modeling environment that enables the generation of variations of one cross-section in a short time.

3 Methodology

The present study employs a parametric design environment to convert a 2D cross-sectional drawing of a window into a 3D model. Relationships between window parts are identified through collision analysis, using geometric relations and matrix-based data processing. To explore the role of graph-based representations in developing disassembly sequences, the methodology begins with generating 3D window models from 2D drawings. These models are used to determine geometry-based precedence relations among parts. Subsequently, graph-based data are represented in matrix form, with particular attention to adjacency and incidence matrices. Material and interface types are then assigned to each parts to ensure the approach accounts for material characteristics and connection types. Weight computation follows a structural complexity assessment method well-established in the literature [8], [9]. For materials, weights range from 0 (low recyclability) to 1 (high recyclability). Aluminum is assigned a weight of 1.0, while the thermal break is assigned 0.1, reflecting their respective recyclability. Interface types are weighted based on four factors: Connection Type (CT), Connection Accessibility (CA), Independency (ID), and Geometry of the Product Edge (GPE). For instance, in this study, the aluminum-aluminum (mechanical) interface uses screw connections (CT=0.8, CA=1.0), resulting in an average weight of 0.9. The aluminum-thermal break interface averages ID=0.4 (incidental intersection) and GPE=0.4 (overlap). The thermal break-thermal break interface averages CA=0.1 (not accessible), ID=0.1 (full integration), and GPE=0.1 (closed), resulting in a final weight of 0.1.

Once material and interface weights were assigned, we prefer a heuristic-hybrid algorithm combining graph traversal techniques with a directional binary connection matrix. This matrix, generated from the as-parsed part relationships, was used to construct a shortest-path tree from a starting node (representing a window part) via dependency-first traversal. The algorithm prioritizes higher index neighbors and selects the nearest unvisited neighbor at each step, thereby forming a single continuous disassembly path that visits all nodes exactly once. This process is analogous to the Traveling Salesman Problem but adapted for deterministic, material-sensitive disassembly sequencing. We

adapted Dijkstra’s shortest-path algorithm into a greedy variant, which selects the locally optimal next step while minimizing total travel distance and cost. The algorithm avoids branching and multiple paths, ensuring a complete and linear disassembly sequence. Material and interface priorities are incorporated through weighted adjacency and incidence matrices, enabling sensitivity to recyclability and connection complexity. The role of graph-based representation, particularly adjacency and incidence matrices, was examined under both weighted and unweighted conditions. The proposed parametric approach was tested on 3D window models of varying complexity (8, 16, 20 parts). This stepwise methodology allowed for direct comparison of disassembly performance across scales and material heterogeneity. Four data configurations were evaluated: unweighted adjacency, weighted adjacency, unweighted incidence, and weighted incidence matrices. Initial validation was performed on three window models, followed by application to increasingly complex assemblies. We plan to extend the analysis to ten window configurations with diverse cross-section details, part counts, and window types, including single-vent and fixed models. The approach is implemented within the Rhinoceros-Grasshopper parametric design environment.

4 Results

We applied adjacency and incidence matrices to evaluate the role of matrix type in disassembly sequence planning under unweighted and weighted traversal schemes to an 8-part assembled 3D window model. Two material combinations are tested: homogeneous (all aluminum) and heterogeneous (aluminum-thermal break combination) within weighted and unweighted adjacency and incidence matrices. Minor differences are observed between adjacency and incidence matrix inputs to Dijkstra’s Greedy Traversal algorithm; however, weighting based on material and interface types notably altered disassembly sequences in mixed-material assemblies. In the heterogeneous case, the weighted matrix differed from the unweighted one, prioritizing aluminum material and aluminum-aluminum connections due to stronger separation weights rather than lower thermal break-thermal break interfaces. On the other hand, in the homogeneous case where all parts were aluminum, weighted and unweighted paths overlapped each other, as all weights were uniform (0.9), as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Disassembly sequences of adjacency and incidence within unweighted and weighted matrices for eight-part window

After evaluating the 8-part window, we applied the proposed framework to a 16-part window model, which increased material diversity by incorporating more thermal break parts. More complex disassembly sequence plans are observed, particularly within weighted adjacency and incidence matrices, which tend to produce more notable results. Due to varied material and interface types (aluminum-aluminum (0.9), aluminum-thermal break (0.4), and thermal break-thermal break (0.10)), Dijkstra’s Greedy Traversal algorithm generated disassembly sequences more aggressively based on interface weights in these weighted matrices (Figure 2). Dissimilarity between adjacency and incidence matrix-based disassembly sequence development begins to emerge in terms of traversal efficiency and order.

Figure 2: Disassembly sequences of adjacency and incidence under unweighted and weighted matrices for sixteen-part window

We, again, defined the start with 'node 4' for each of these disassembly sequence developments. As expected, we observed that unweighted disassembly sequences of the adjacency matrix-based approach [4, 6, 5, 0, 1, 2, 3, 8, 9, 7, 10, 12, 11, 14, 15, 13] and the incidence-based approach [4, 7, 10, 13, 6, 5, 0, 1, 2, 3, 8, 11, 14, 12, 9, 15] followed a topological/geometric pattern without sensitivity to material and interface types. Small differences between the two matrix types arose from the traversal order due to node-to-node and node-to-edge relations when nodes have equal distances in the graph. From the weighted matrices point of view, a weighted adjacency matrix-based sequence is generated

as [4, 6, 5, 0, 1, 2, 3, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15] and a weighted incidence matrix-based sequence as [4, 7, 10, 13, 6, 5, 0, 1, 2, 3, 8, 11, 14, 9, 12, 15]. These sequences reflect the role of material and interface types in prioritizing strong (aluminum-aluminum) connections, delaying lower weights. This prioritization demonstrates that Dijkstra's Greedy Traversal algorithm prioritizes material and interface types, minimizing disassembly effort by postponing weaker or mixed joints. As a result, weighted matrices provide logically better and more comprehensive disassembly sequences.

Full disassembly path (unweighted): [4, 0, 3, 2, 1, 6, 7, 8, 5, 9, 10, 13, 12, 11, 16, 17, 14, 15, 18, 19]

Full disassembly path (weighted): [4, 0, 5, 10, 15, 3, 2, 1, 6, 7, 11, 12, 16, 17, 13, 8, 9, 14, 19, 18]

Full disassembly path (unweighted): [4, 0, 2, 1, 3, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19]

Full disassembly path (weighted): [4, 0, 5, 10, 15, 2, 1, 6, 7, 11, 12, 16, 17, 3, 8, 9, 13, 14, 18, 19]

Figure 3: Disassembly sequences of adjacency and incidence under unweighted and weighted matrices for twenty-part window

Once and for all, we extended our window model part numbers to 20 and evaluated the proposed approach under unweighted and weighted adjacency and incidence matrices. Similarly, the 8-part window and 16-part window, as well as unweighted matrices, generate topological disassembly sequences that are insensitive to material and interface types. Nodes, which are window parts, are visited in a generally sequential or radial order based on geometric relations. However, weighted matrices prioritized material and interface type relations, assigning higher weights to aluminum and aluminum-aluminum interfaces, followed by weaker weights. Nodes like 0, 1, 2, 6, 7, 11, and 12 appeared on the disassembly sequence list earlier due to stronger (aluminum-aluminum) relations

(Figure 3). Nodes with more thermal break material and interface types appeared later. Herein, the incidence matrix generates similar but not identical weighted sequences compared to the adjacency matrix. This showed that incidence matrices are more sensitive to edge-based characteristics than adjacency matrices.

5 Discussion

To evaluate different disassembly sequence planning strategies, simulations were conducted on aluminum-thermal break windows with 8, 16, and 29 parts. Using a greedy adaptation of Dijkstra's algorithm, both adjacency and incidence matrices were tested under unweighted and weighted conditions. Material-based weights modeled separation complexity, enabling realistic sequence planning. Unweighted matrices produced similar sequences regardless of material type, reflecting purely geometric and topological relationships. Adjacency matrices emphasized part-to-part relations, while incidence matrices captured more part-to-joint relations, offering finer control over traversal paths. The latter proved more sensitive to shared interfaces, an advantage in complex assemblies where multiple parts meet. Weighted matrices incorporated material-interface logic, prioritizing disassembly according to connection strength ($0.9 > 0.4 > 0.1$). Stronger connections, such as aluminum-aluminum, were removed first, while weaker ones, such as aluminum-thermal break or thermal break-thermal break, were delayed. This behavior confirms the method's sensitivity to both structural arrangement and material-specific interface properties, demonstrating that Dijkstra's algorithm effectively uses weight data to minimize disassembly effort.

6 Conclusion

This study presents a graph-based disassembly sequence planning approach for aluminum-framed windows, utilizing Dijkstra's Greedy Traversal algorithm within adjacency and incidence matrices under both unweighted and weighted conditions. The results show that while unweighted matrices produce disassembly sequences primarily governed by geometry and topological relations, weighted matrices generate material-sensitive sequences, allowing the algorithm to compute not just geometrically optimal but also material- and effort-aware disassembly sequences. Another key finding is that incidence matrices yield more edge-sensitive results for controlling joint-level disassembly relations than adjacency matrix results. The use of weighted matrices results in more realistic disassembly sequences, aligning with practical expectations for developing disassembly sequences for multilayer and multi-material windows. The proposed framework was validated for robustness and scalability, even for windows with increasing complexity, with 8, 16, and 20 parts. In conclusion, this study shows the practical implications of using graph theory-based models within (un-)weighted traversal algorithms for disassembly sequence planning in parametric design contexts. The proposed framework not only enables a more material- and geometry-informed disassembly sequence planning process but also supports material recovery strategies, making it highly applicable in real-world manufacturing scenarios.

Acknowledgements

We gratefully acknowledge support from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 101056773 for funding this work under the Reincarnate project.

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